

TABLE-1 ABSORPTION BANDS AND DESCRIPTION OF THEIR CONTOURS.

Hydroquinone H.A	2.9-3.0 μ broad	3.45 μ hump	5.85 μ hump	6.25 μ sharp	7.15 μ sharp	—	8.2-8.6 μ broad	—
Catechol H.A. (O ₂)	2.9-3.3 broad μ	3.45 μ sharp	5.85 μ weak	6.25 μ m. sharp	—	7.25 μ V. weak	8.2-8.6 μ broad	—
Hydrolysed catechol H.A. (Residue)	3.2 μ broad	—	5.85 μ hump	6.25 μ sharp	—	7.25 μ V. weak	8.45 μ shoulder	—
Hydrolysed hydroquinone H.A. (Residue)	2.9-3.3 μ broad	—	5.85 μ hump	6.25 μ sharp	—	—	8.0-8.5 μ broad	—
Hydroquinoneglycine polymer	3.0-3.3 μ broad	—	5.85 μ V. weak hump	6.25 μ sharp	6.65 μ V. sharp	7.45 μ V. weak	8.0-8.5 μ broad	—
Hydrolysed hydroquinone glycine polymer (Residue)	3.0-3.3 μ broad	—	5.85 μ V. weak hump	6.25 μ sharp	6.65 μ V. sharp	7.45 μ V. weak	8.0-8.5 μ broad	—
Glucose H.A. (40 hr)	2.9-3.2 μ broad	3.45 μ shoulder	5.85 μ V. sharp	6.25 μ sharp	6.65 μ sharp	7.25 μ weak	8.2-8.6 μ broad	9.8 μ sharp
Glucose H.A.	2.9-3.2 μ broad	3.45 μ hump	5.85 μ sharp	6.25 μ sharp	6.6 μ hump	7.25 μ broad	8.2-8.6 μ shoulder	9.8 μ sharp
Glucose hyatomelanic acid	2.9-3.2 broad	3.45 μ sharp	5.85 μ sharp	6.25 μ sharp	6.6 μ sharp	7.2 μ weak	8.3 μ broad	9.8 μ weak
Hydrolysed catechol H.A. (by O ₂) (Residue)	2.9-3.4 μ broad	—	5.85 μ weak	6.25 μ sharp	—	—	8.4 μ shoulder	—

TABLE 2 ANALYSIS OF I.R. SPECTRA OF SYNTHETIC HUMIC SUBSTANCES.

Wave length (μ)	Proposed assignment
2.9-3.0	H—bonded OH
3.3	Aromatic CH
3.4-3.5	Aliphatic CH ₂ and CH ₃
5.8-5.9	Vibration of carboxyl C=O (carbonyl) in aromatic and aliphatic acids.
6.25	Stretching vibrations of conjugated C=C carbon bonds, C=O in quinones, stretching vibrations of —C=N—in heterocyclic nitrogen compounds.
6.6-6.7	Aromatic C=C.
7.15	CH stretch of methyl
7.25-7.3	Aliphatic CH ₂ and CH ₃
8.-8.5	C—O—C stretch frequencies of aromatic ethers.
9.8	—C—, —C—OH—and—C—C—C— vibrations typical of sugar rings and glucosidic linkages.

From the spectra, the presence of the following groups has been suggested: Polymerically bonded-OH groups, free carboxyl and carboxylate groups, side chain CH₂ and CH₃ groups and c=c-vibrations of aromatic ring system. From the study made here it can be said that inspite of different starting materials as well as different techniques of preparations, the synthetic humic acids resemble closely each other in their i. r spectra and also they have striking similarities in this respect with their natural counterpart.

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Oxine Complexes of Quinquevalent Molybdenum-Di-8 hydroxyquinolinium Oxopentabromomolybdate(V) and its derivatives.

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IN continuation of our investigation on the co-ordination chemistry of molybdenum we report here the isolation and study of oxine complexes of quinquevalent molybdenum. It is already known¹⁻² that the chemistry of molybdenum in oxidation state five is mainly dominated by the oxometal ions MoO³⁺, Mo₂O₃⁴⁺ and Mo₂O₄²⁺. We have isolated (Oxine H₂)₂ [MoOBr₅] and [Mo₂O₄ (Oxine)₂ (H₂O)₂] (where oxineH = 8-hydroxyquinoline) and characterised them by analytical and various other by physicochemical methods.

Experimental

All reagents used were of A. R. grade. *Analyses*: Molybdenum and bromine were estimated³ gravimetrically as MoO₃ and AgBr respectively. Nitrogen was estimated by Dumas' method.

Preparation Di-8-hydroxy quinolinium oxopentabromomolybdate (V), (OxineH₂)₂[MoOBr₅]: 1g of molybdenum trioxide was dissolved in 15 ml of concentrated hydrobromic acid (48%) with gentle heating and the solution was evaporated to brown moist solid. This was taken up in solution with 10 ml of hydrobromic acid and to this was added 5 ml hydrobromic acid solution of 1.5g of 8-hydroxyquino-

Fig. 1. Electronic spectra of (Oxine H₂) [MoOBr₅] in 9M HBr.

line with stirring. This was cooled in freezing mixture when greenish yellow precipitate of the compound appeared. This was filtered, recrystallised from hydrobromic acid and dried in vacuum over solid KOH to constant weight, yield 3g.

Found: Mo, 11.48%; Br, 49.97%; N, 3.49%

Calculated for C₁₃H₁₆N₂O₂ [MoOBr₅], Mo, 11.93%; Br, 49.73%; N, 3.48%. Oxidation state of the metal determined by modified ceric sulphate method was +5.

Oxo-μ-dioxoquo (8-hydroxyquinolinato) molybdenum (V), [Mo₂O₄ (Oxine)₂ (H₂O)₂]: 2g of (Oxine H₂)₂ [MoOBr₅] was slowly boiled with 100 ml water when there was immediate precipitation of a pink solid. This was filtered, washed with water and dried as before, yield 0.5g.

Found: Mo, 32.90%; N, 4.59%; oxidation state of Mo, +5.

Calculated for [Mo₂O₄ (oxine)₂ (H₂O)₂], Mo, 32.98%; N, 4.81%.

Properties: Conductivity measurements of the salt (OxineH₂)₂ [MoOBr₅] in aqueous medium show that it is extensively hydrolysed and ionised. But the molar conductance of the derivative in acetonitrile is much less than that of a binary electrolyte Δ=8.5 ohm⁻¹ cm² for 10⁻³M solution, which indicates the nonelectrolytic nature of the compound. The salt (μ_{eff}=1.55 B. M. at 33°) contains molybdenum in quinquevalent state. The nonelectrolytic compound is diamagnetic due to the presence of oxobridged species Mo₂O₄²⁺. Infrared spectra of these compounds clearly show the ν(M=O) frequency at 991 cm⁻¹ and 961 cm⁻¹. The broad bands in the region 700-800 cm⁻¹ may be traced as metal-oxygen chain (-Mo-O-Mo-O) vibrations² in the nonelectrolytic species.

Electronic spectra: The spectra of the salt (OxineH₂)₂ [MoOBr₅] was taken in 9 M HBr and the nonelectrolytic compound [Mo₂O₄(Oxine)₂ (H₂O)₂] in acetonitrile. The results are tabulated in Table I.

TABLE I			
Compound	λ _{max} in μ	ν × 10 ⁻⁸ in cm ⁻¹	ε _{molar} extinction
(Oxine H) ₂ [MoOBr ₅]	695	14.3	14
	469	21.3	519
	408	24.5	3800
	370	27.0	5950
	308	32.4	7510
	254	39.3	1007
	538	18.5	168
[Mo ₂ O ₄ (Oxine)(HO)]	384	26.0	660
	312	32.0	840
	246	40.6	4620

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Chalcones XIII : Potential Germicides derived from Substituted Acetophenones

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THE antimicrobial and toxic action of amino, hydroxy, methoxy, and halo Chalcones have been reported by a few workers¹⁻¹³. The antibacterial and germicidal activity of these compounds is due to conjugated systems^{2,8-10}. These results have prompted us to synthesise several chalcones with a view to study their and other biological activity. The various substituent, present in the nucleus, by changing their position from ortho to meta and then to para extends the length of the conjugated system. This may reinforce the germicidal activity of compounds.

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